

IKKINCHI TARTIBLI CHIZIQLARNING UMUMIY TENGLAMASINI KANONIK SHAKLGA KELTIRISH

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Annatsiya. Ushbu ishda ikkinchi tartibli chiziqlarning umumiy tenglamasi va ikkinchi tartibli chiziqning umumiy tenglamasidagi koeffitsientlar qanday bo‘lganda ellipsni, giperbolani, parabolani ifodalashi o‘rganiladi hamda ikkinchi tartibli chiziqning xarakteristik tenglamasi qaraladi.

Kalit so‘z: ikkinchi tartibli chiziq. Xarakteristik tenglama. Reper.

Аннотация. В данной работе изучаются общее уравнение линий второго порядка и коэффициенты в общем уравнении линии второго порядка для выражения эллипса, гиперболы, параболы, а также рассматривается характеристическое уравнение линии второго порядка.

Ключевое слово: линия второго порядка. Характеристическое уравнение Репера.

Abstract. In this work, the general equation of the second-order lines and the coefficients in the general equation of the second-order line are studied to express the ellipse, hyperbola, parabola, and the characteristic equation of the second-order line is considered.

Keyword: second-order line. Characteristic equation. Reper.

Tekislikda biror affin (yoki Dekart) repyerda koordinatalari

$$a_{11}x^2 + 2a_{12}xy + a_{22}y^2 + 2a_{10}x + 2a_{20}y + a_{00} = 0 \quad (1)$$

tenglamani qanoatlantiruvchi nuqtalar to‘plami ikkinchi tartibli chiziq deb atalishi ma‘lum. Bunda a_{11} , a_{12} , a_{22} , a_{10} , a_{20} , a_{00} koeffitsientlar haqiqiy sonlar bo‘lib, a_{11} , a_{12} , a_{22} lardan kamida bittasi noldan farqlidir (bu shartni bundan buyon $a_{11}^2 + a_{12}^2 + a_{22}^2 \neq 0$ ko‘rinishida yozamiz).

Bizga ma‘lumki uchta chiziq: ellips, giperbola va parabola ikkinchi tartibli chiziqlardir, chunki (1) tenglamada $a_{11} = \frac{1}{a^2}$, $a_{22} = \frac{1}{b^2}$, $a_{00} = -1$ bo‘lib, qolgan barcha koeffitsientlar nol

bo‘lsa, u ellipsning kanonik tenglamasi, shu shartlarda yana $a_{22} = -\frac{1}{b^2}$ bo‘lsa, (1) tenglama giperbolaning kanonik tenglamasi, $a_{10} = p$; $a_{22} = 1$ bo‘lib, qolgan koeffitsientlar nol bo‘lsa, (1) tenglama parabolaning kanonik tenglamasidir.

Quyidagi tabiiy savol tug‘iladi: tekislikda ko‘rilgan bu chiziqlardan boshqa yana ikkinchi tartibli chiziqlar bormi? Bu savolga quyida javob berishga harakat qilamiz. Avvalo shuni ta‘kidlaymiz bizga ma‘lumki, chiziqning tartibi koordinatalar sistemasining olinishiga bog‘liq emas. Bundan foydalanib, koordinatalar sistemasini tegishlicha tanlash hisobiga barcha ikkinchi tartibli chiziqni to‘la geometrik tavsiflab chiqamiz. Ikkinchi tartibli γ chiziq $\beta = (O, \vec{i}, \vec{j})$ dekart repyerida (1) umumiy tenglamasi bilan ifodalangan bo‘lsin. Shunday repyeri tanlaymizki, unga nisbatan γ chiziqning (1) tenglamasi mumkin qadar sodda – «kanonik» ko‘rinishga ega bo‘lsin, ya‘ni

1) o‘zgaruvchi koordinatalar ko‘paytmasi qatnashgan had bo‘lmasin;

- 2) birinchi darajali hadlar soni eng oz bo'lsin (iloji bo'lsa, ular butunlay qatnashmasin);
3) mumkin bo'lsa, ozod had qatnashmasin.

Agar (1) tenglamada $a_{12} \neq 0$ bo'lsa, soddalashtirishni quyidagicha bajaramiz. β reperning o'qlarini O nuqta atrofida ixtiyoriy α burchakka burib, yangi $\beta' = (O, \vec{i}', \vec{j}')$ dekart reperini hosil qilamiz. β repyerdan β' repenga o'tish formulalari

$$\begin{cases} x = x' \cos \alpha - y' \sin \alpha, \\ y = x' \sin \alpha + y' \cos \alpha \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

dan x, y ni (1) ga qo'ysak va o'xshash hadlarini ixchamlasak, γ chiziqning (1) tenglamasiga β' repyerdan ushbu ko'rinishni oladi:

$$a'_{11}x'^2 + 2a'_{12}x'y' + a'_{22}y'^2 + 2a'_{10}x' + 2a'_{20}y' + a'_{00} = 0, \quad (3)$$

bunda:

$$\begin{aligned} a'_{11} &= a_{11} \cos^2 \alpha + 2a_{12} \cos \alpha \sin \alpha + a_{22} \sin^2 \alpha, \\ a'_{12} &= -a_{11} \sin \alpha \cos \alpha + a_{12} \cos^2 \alpha - a_{12} \sin^2 \alpha + a_{22} \sin \alpha \cos \alpha, \\ a'_{22} &= a_{11} \sin^2 \alpha - 2a_{12} \sin \alpha \cos \alpha + a_{22} \cos^2 \alpha, \\ a'_{10} &= a_{10} \cos \alpha + a_{20} \sin \alpha, \quad a'_{20} = -a_{10} \sin \alpha + a_{20} \cos \alpha, \quad a'_{00} = a_{00}. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

(4) belgilashlardan ko'rinadiki, (3) tenglamadagi $a'_{11}, a'_{12}, a'_{22}$ koefitsientlar (1) tenglamadagi a_{11}, a_{12}, a_{22} koefitsientlarga va α burchakka bog'liq, shu bilan birga $a'_{11}, a'_{12}, a'_{22}$ ning kamida biri noldan farqli, chunki

$$\begin{aligned} &\begin{vmatrix} \cos^2 \alpha & 2 \cos \alpha \sin \alpha & \sin^2 \alpha \\ -\sin \alpha \cos \alpha & \cos^2 \alpha - \sin^2 \alpha & \sin \alpha \cos \alpha \\ \sin^2 \alpha & -2 \sin \alpha \cos \alpha & \cos^2 \alpha \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} \cos^2 \alpha & \sin 2\alpha & \sin^2 \alpha \\ -\frac{1}{2} \sin 2\alpha & \cos 2\alpha & \frac{1}{2} \sin 2\alpha \\ \sin^2 \alpha & -\sin 2\alpha & \cos^2 \alpha \end{vmatrix} = \\ &= \begin{vmatrix} \cos^2 \alpha & \sin 2\alpha & \sin^2 \alpha \\ -\frac{1}{2} \sin 2\alpha & \cos 2\alpha & \frac{1}{2} \sin 2\alpha \\ 1 & 0 & 1 \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} \cos^2 \alpha & \sin 2\alpha & 1 \\ -\frac{1}{2} \sin 2\alpha & \cos 2\alpha & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 2 \end{vmatrix} = \\ &= 2 \cos^2 \alpha \cos 2\alpha - \cos 2\alpha + \sin^2 2\alpha = \cos 2\alpha (2 \cos^2 \alpha - \sin^2 \alpha - \cos^2 \alpha) + \sin^2 2\alpha = \\ &= \cos 2\alpha \cdot \cos 2\alpha + \sin^2 2\alpha = 1 \neq 0. \end{aligned}$$

α burchakning ixtiyoriyligidan foydalanib, uni shunday tanlab olamizki, almashtirilgan (3) tenglamadagi a'_{12} koefitsient nolga teng bo'lsin, ya'ni

$$\begin{aligned} a'_{12} &= -a_{11} \sin \alpha \cos \alpha + a_{12} \cos^2 \alpha - a_{12} \sin^2 \alpha + a_{22} \sin \alpha \cos \alpha = \\ &= -(a_{11} \cos \alpha + a_{12} \sin \alpha) \sin \alpha + (a_{21} \cos \alpha + a_{22} \sin \alpha) \cos \alpha = 0 \end{aligned}$$

yoki

$$\frac{a_{11} \cos \alpha + a_{12} \sin \alpha}{\cos \alpha} = \frac{a_{21} \cos \alpha + a_{22} \sin \alpha}{\sin \alpha}. \quad (5)$$

(5) munosabatni biror λ ga tenglab, uni quyidagi ko'rinishda yozish mumkin:

$$\begin{cases} (a_{11} - \lambda)\cos \alpha + a_{12} \sin \alpha = 0, \\ a_{21} \cos \alpha + (a_{22} - \lambda)\sin \alpha = 0. \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Bu sistema bir jinsli, shuning uchun uning determinanti nolga teng, ya'ni

$$\begin{vmatrix} a_{11} - \lambda & a_{12} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} - \lambda \end{vmatrix} = 0 \quad \text{yoki} \quad \lambda^2 - (a_{11} + a_{22})\lambda + (a_{11}a_{22} - a_{12}^2) = 0 \quad (7)$$

bo'lgandagina sistema noldan farqli yechimga ega bo'ladi.

(7) tenglama γ chiziqning *xarakteristik tenglamasi* deyiladi.

(7) tenglamaning ildizlari:

$$\lambda_{1,2} = \frac{(a_{11} + a_{22}) \pm \sqrt{(a_{11} + a_{22})^2 - 4(a_{11}a_{22} - a_{12}^2)}}{2} = \frac{(a_{11} + a_{22}) \pm \sqrt{D}}{2}.$$

$a_{12} \neq 0$ bo'lgani uchun uning diskriminanti:

$$D = (a_{11} + a_{22})^2 - 4(a_{11}a_{22} - a_{12}^2) = (a_{11} - a_{22})^2 + 4a_{12}^2 > 0.$$

Demak, (6) tenglamaning λ_1, λ_2 ildizlari turli va haqiqiydir. (5) dan

$$\begin{cases} a_{11} \cos \alpha + a_{12} \sin \alpha = \lambda \cos \alpha, \\ a_{21} \cos \alpha + a_{22} \sin \alpha = \lambda \sin \alpha \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

tengliklarni yoza olamiz. Ularning har birini $\cos \alpha \neq 0$ ga bo'lib, $\cos \alpha = 0 \Rightarrow \alpha = \frac{\pi}{2}$

va $a'_{12} = -(a_{11} \cos \alpha + a_{12} \sin \alpha) \sin \alpha + (a_{21} \cos \alpha + a_{22} \sin \alpha) \cos \alpha = 0 \Rightarrow a_{12} = 0$,

(ya'ni a_{12} azaldan 0 ga teng ekan) ushbu hosil qilamiz:

$$\operatorname{tg} \alpha = \frac{\lambda - a_{11}}{a_{12}} = \frac{a_{21}}{\lambda - a_{22}}. \quad (9)$$

(9) munosabatga navbat bilan (7) xarakteristik tenglamaning λ_1, λ_2 ildizlarini qo'yamiz:

$$\operatorname{tg} \alpha_1 = \frac{\lambda_1 - a_{11}}{a_{12}}, \quad \operatorname{tg} \alpha_2 = \frac{\lambda_2 - a_{11}}{a_{12}}. \quad (10)$$

Viyet teoremasiga ko'ra (7) dan

$$\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 = a_{11} + a_{22}, \quad \lambda_1 \lambda_2 = a_{11}a_{22} - a_{12}^2. \quad (11)$$

(11) va (10) formulalardan ushbuga ega bo'lamiz:

$$\operatorname{tg} \alpha_1 \cdot \operatorname{tg} \alpha_2 = \frac{\lambda_1 \lambda_2 - a_{11}(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2) + a_{11}^2}{a_{12}^2} = -1 \Rightarrow |\alpha_2 - \alpha_1| = \frac{\pi}{2}.$$

Shunga ko'ra $\operatorname{tg} \alpha$ Ox' o'qning β dagi burchak koeffitsienti bo'lganda

$\operatorname{tg} \alpha_2 = \operatorname{tg} \left(\alpha_1 + \frac{\pi}{2} \right)$ Oy' o'qning shu repyerdagi burchak koeffitsienti bo'ladi. U holda Ox'

o'qning $\vec{i}$ birlik vektorining koordinatalari bo'lmish $\cos \alpha_1, \sin \alpha_1$,

$$\sin \alpha_1 = \frac{\operatorname{tg} \alpha_1}{\sqrt{1 + \operatorname{tg}^2 \alpha_1}}, \quad \cos \alpha_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \operatorname{tg}^2 \alpha_1}}$$

formulalardan, Oy' o'qning $\vec{j}'$ birlik vektorining koordinatalari $\cos \alpha_2, \sin \alpha_2$

$$\sin \alpha_2 = \sin\left(\alpha_1 + \frac{\pi}{2}\right) = \cos \alpha_1, \quad \cos \alpha_2 = \cos\left(\alpha_1 + \frac{\pi}{2}\right) = -\sin \alpha_1$$

tenglklardan aniqlanadi. $\lambda = \lambda_1$ bo'lganda (8) dan

$$a_{11} \cos \alpha_1 + a_{12} \sin \alpha_1 = \lambda_1 \cos \alpha_1,$$

$$a_{21} \cos \alpha_1 + a_{22} \sin \alpha_1 = \lambda_1 \sin \alpha_1,$$

u holda

$$\begin{aligned} a'_{11} &= (a_{11} \cos \alpha_1 + a_{12} \sin \alpha_1) \cos \alpha_1 + (a_{21} \cos \alpha_1 + a_{22} \sin \alpha_1) \sin \alpha_1 = \\ &= \lambda_1 \cos \alpha_1 \cos \alpha_1 + \lambda_1 \sin \alpha_1 \sin \alpha_1 = \lambda. \end{aligned}$$

(4) munosabatda 1- va 3- tengliklarni hadlab qo'shsak, $a'_{11} + a'_{22} = a_{11}(\sin^2 \alpha + \cos^2 \alpha) + a_{22}(\sin^2 \alpha + \cos^2 \alpha)$ yoki $a'_{11} + a'_{22} = a_{11} + a_{22}$. (11) dan $a_{11} + a_{22} = \lambda_1 + \lambda_2$ va $a'_{11} = \lambda_1$ ekanini hisobga olsak, $a'_{22} = \lambda_2$ kelib chiqadi. Shunday qilib, koordinatalar sistemasini (10) formuladan aniqlanuvchi $\alpha = \alpha_1$ burchakka (bu yerda α_1 yangi Ox' o'qning eski Ox o'qqa og'ish burchagi) burish bilan $\beta = (O, \vec{i}, \vec{j})$ repyerdan shunday $\beta' = (O, \vec{i}', \vec{j}')$ repyerga o'tish mumkinki, unga nisbatan (1) tenglama soddalashib, ushbu ko'rinishga ega bo'ladi:

$$\lambda_1 x'^2 + \lambda_2 y'^2 + 2a'_{10}x' + 2a'_{20}y' + a_{00} = 0. \quad (12)$$

Agar Ox' o'qning burchak koeffitsienti uchun $\operatorname{tg} \alpha_2 = \frac{\lambda_2 - a_{11}}{a_{12}}$ ni qabul qilinsa, u

holda $a'_{11} = \lambda_2$, $a'_{22} = \lambda_1$ ekanini aynan yuqoridagi kabi ko'rsatish mumkin. Shuni aytish lozimki, agar (1) tenglamada $a_{12} = 0$ bo'lsa, koordinatalar sistemasini burish bilan almashtirishga hojat qolmaydi.

Endi $\beta' = (O, \vec{i}', \vec{j}')$ repyerdan shunday repyerga o'tamizki, unga nisbatan γ chiziqning (12) tenglamasida birinchi darajali hadlar qatnashmasin. Bu ishni koordinatalar boshini ko'chirish bilan bajarish mumkin.

(12) tenglamada λ_1, λ_2 koeffitsientlarning kamida biri noldan farqli, chunki agar $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = 0$ bo'lsa, (12) tenglama birinchi darajali tenglamaga aylanar edi. Demak, bu yerda quyidagi uch hol bo'lishi mumkin:

$$1. \lambda_1 \neq 0, \quad \lambda_2 \neq 0 \quad (\lambda_1 \lambda_2 \neq 0)$$

Bu holda $\lambda_1 \lambda_2 = a_{11} a_{22} - a_{12}^2 \Rightarrow a_{11} a_{22} - a_{12}^2 \neq 0$. (12) tenglamaning chap tomonidagi hadlarni x', y' ga nisbatan to'liq kvadratga keltiramiz:

$$\lambda_1 \left(x'^2 + 2 \cdot \frac{a'_{10}}{\lambda_1} x' + \frac{a'^2_{10}}{\lambda_1^2} \right) + \lambda_2 \left(y'^2 + 2 \cdot \frac{a'_{20}}{\lambda_2} y' + \frac{a'^2_{20}}{\lambda_2^2} \right) - \frac{a'^2_{10}}{\lambda_1} - \frac{a'^2_{20}}{\lambda_2} + a_{00} = 0,$$

bundan

$$\lambda_1 \left(x' + \frac{a'_{10}}{\lambda_1} \right)^2 + \lambda_2 \left(y' + \frac{a'_{20}}{\lambda_2} \right)^2 + a''_{00} = 0, \quad (13)$$

bu yerda $a''_{00} = a_{00} - \frac{a'^2_{10}}{\lambda_1} - \frac{a'^2_{20}}{\lambda_2}$.

Endi $(O, \vec{i}', \vec{j}')$ ni u quyidagi formula bilan aniqlanadigan parallel ko'chirishni bajaraylik:

$$\begin{cases} X = x' + \frac{a'_{10}}{\lambda_1}, \\ Y = y' + \frac{a'_{20}}{\lambda_2}. \end{cases} \quad (*)$$

U holda yangi $(O, \vec{i}', \vec{j}')$ reper hosil bo'lib, chiziqning tenglamasi soddalashadi:

$$\lambda_1 X^2 + \lambda_2 Y^2 + a''_{00} = 0. \quad (14)$$

2. $\lambda_1 = 0 (\lambda_2 \neq 0)$, $a'_{10} \neq 0$ yoki $\lambda_2 = 0 (\lambda_1 \neq 0)$, $a'_{20} \neq 0$.

Bu hollardan birini ko'rsatish etarli; chunki

$$\begin{cases} x = y', \\ y = x' \end{cases}$$

almashtirish yordamida ularning birini ikkinchisiga keltirish mumkin.

Birinchi holni qaraymiz:

$\lambda_1 = 0 (\lambda_2 \neq 0)$ ni hisobga olib, (12) tenglamaning chap tomonidagi hadlarni y' ga nisbatan to'liq kvadratga keltiramiz:

$$\lambda_2 \left(y'^2 + 2 \cdot \frac{a'_{20}}{\lambda_2} y' + \frac{a'^2_{20}}{\lambda_2^2} \right) + 2a'_{10} \left(x' + \frac{a_{00}}{2a'_{10}} - \frac{a'^2_{20}}{2a'_{10}\lambda_2} \right) = 0,$$

yoki

$$\lambda_2 \left(y' + \frac{a'_{20}}{\lambda_2} \right)^2 + 2a'_{10} (x' + a') = 0,$$

bunda $a' = \frac{a_{00}}{2a'_{10}} - \frac{a'^2_{20}}{2a'_{10}\lambda_2}$ belgilashni kiritdik.

Ushbu

$$\begin{cases} X = x' + a', \\ Y = y' + \frac{a'_{20}}{\lambda_2} \end{cases}$$

formular bo'yicha koordinatalar sistemasini almashtiramiz, ya'ni koordinatalar boshi O ni $O' \left(a', \frac{a'_{20}}{\lambda_2} \right)$ nuqtaga ko'chiramiz. U holda hosil bo'lgan $(O, \vec{i}', \vec{j}')$ reperga nisbatan chiziqning tenglamasi ushbu sodda ko'rinishni qabul qiladi:

$$\lambda_2 Y^2 + 2a'_{10} X = 0. \quad (15)$$

3. $\lambda_1 = 0, a'_{10} = 0$ yoki $\lambda_2 = 0, a'_{20} = 0$.

Bu hollar ham bir-biriga o'xshash bo'lib, shuning uchun ularning birini qarash etarli.

Birinchi holni qaraymiz. $\lambda_1 = 0, a'_{10} = 0$ da (12) tenglama ushbu ko'rinishni oladi:

$$\lambda_2 y'^2 + 2a'_{20} y' + a_{00} = 0, \quad (16)$$

bu yerda $\lambda_2 \neq 0$ bo'lgani uchun (16) ni quyidagicha yozish mumkin:

$$\lambda_2 \left(y'^2 + 2 \cdot \frac{a'_{20}}{\lambda_2} y' + \frac{a'^2_{20}}{\lambda_2^2} \right) - \frac{a'^2_{20}}{\lambda_2} + a_{00} = 0$$

yoki

$$\lambda_2 \left(y' + \frac{a'_{20}}{\lambda_2} \right)^2 + a''_{00} = 0,$$

bunda
$$a''_{00} = a_{00} - \frac{a'^2_{20}}{\lambda_2}.$$

Ushbu
$$\begin{cases} X = x' \\ Y = y' + \frac{a'_{20}}{\lambda_2} \end{cases}$$
 formulalar bo'yicha $(O, \vec{i}', \vec{j}')$ repyerdan $O' \left(0, \frac{a'_{20}}{\lambda_2} \right)$ nuqtaga

ko'chiramiz. Yangi repyerda γ chiziqning sodda tenglamasi hosil bo'ladi:

$$\lambda_2 Y^2 + a''_{00} = 0. \quad (17)$$

X ulosa. Agar ikkinchi tartibli γ chiziq biror dekart repyerda (1) tenglama bilan berilgan bo'lsa, yangi dekart reperini tegishlicha tanlash bilan γ ning tenglamasini (14), (15), (17) tenglamalarning biriga keltirish mumkin.

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